

PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SPINAL SPONDYLITIS CAUSED BY COVID-19

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The relevance of the problem, the trend in the treatment of degenerative-dystrophic diseases of the spine in the world are becoming an increasingly urgent task. The spread of the COVID-19 pandemic around the world has become a test for the musculoskeletal system and traumatology. Various chronic orthopedic diseases associated with COVID-19 have become not only the subject of close study, but also one of the most pressing medical and social problems in the region.

Objective: to improve information on clinical, instrumental, morphological and morphometric signs of spinal spondylitis after COVID-19.

Material and methods of the study: To study the topography and morphology of degenerative-dystrophic changes in the spine, chest and lumbar region after covid-19 due to inflammation, conservative spondylitis of the spine in the Ibn Sino clinic in Andijan and a disc from 30 to 65 years old in the autopsy department of the Republican Center for Pathological Anatomy of the Uzbek SSR, we used the material obtained during surgery for hernias and spondylitis.

Results of the study and their discussion: The conclusions on the histological data obtained during the examination were studied and analyzed. Another reason why we study age-related destructive and degenerative diseases of the spine, neck, chest and back is compliance with the priorities of scientific research. With increasing age of patients, uneven loads on the functional areas of the structure, processes causing hormonal changes, and factors causing degenerative pathologies in tissues lead to a violation of the normal morphological state. In case of structural and functional diseases of the spine, constant study of its morphology makes it necessary to conduct a scientific analysis of pathomorphological processes. Based on the studied data, it can be said that the combination of the pathomorphological picture of spinal spondylitis in patients with COVID-19 with clinical analysis data allows us to build a comparative diagnosis. The spine serves as a scientific basis for restoring

human health. Thus, our findings based on the pathomorphology of structural and functional diseases of the spine determine the treatment algorithm.

Conclusion: The patient, under the influence of unprescribed drug therapy, develops various complications from the digestive organs, cardiovascular system. The results of the conducted scientific studies showed that when studying the level of the disease of patients and making the correct diagnosis, it was established that pathomorphological changes should be determined taking into account an individual approach to age, lifestyle and work activity.

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